

Early AI Systems and Programs: The Pioneering 1960s

Like the early quantum mechanics experiments that exposed the strange nature of the atomic world, the 1960's were the period of artificial intelligence's experimental phase. At the beginning of this decade, it was the first practical implementation of some AI concepts that turned theoretical possibilities into working systems.

Early artificial intelligence pioneers in the 1960s were essentially trying to teach a newborn baby how to think logically in a few days. But they hoped to make machines that could duplicate the human thinking process, which we now know is a hard problem, and they attempted them with astonishing optimism and cleverness.

The Logic Theorist (LT): The First AI Program

Background and Development

Mathematical logic was a man-centred notion before LT was born. Although formal systems had been developed that would allow mathematicians like George Boole and Gottlob Frege to formalise logical reasoning, they were still tools for human thought (Gardner, 1958). Really, the idea of machines being able to manipulate these systems on their own was revolutionary.

At the Carnegie Tech—the Carnegie Mellon University—Allen Newell and Herbert Simon were attempting to find out how humans solve problems. Their main contribution was that human problem solving was composed of incremental, programable steps (Newell & Simon, 1972).

Allen Newell, Herbert Simon and Cliff Shaw did what a great chess master would do: in the summer of 1956 when Allen Newell, Herbert Simon and Cliff Shaw created the Logic Theorist (LT), still regarded as the world's first artificial intelligence programme (McCorduck, 2004). The Logic Theorist was designed to help mathematicians to prove logical theorems in the same way that a calculator helps us perform mathematical calculations.

Technical Implementation

IPL is a list processing language designed for LT in which the team developed it. IPL is like a specialist toolkit, like a master craftsman's tool set for completing a particular delegated undertaking. It provided capabilities for:

- Symbol manipulation
- List processing
- Recursive operations
- Pattern matching

It ran on the same principle that humans use to solve puzzles. Like a jigsaw puzzle, say you have a piece of paper with the complete picture on it but it is broken in pieces. Find one piece, place it, and move to the next one again until you get it entirely. Similarly, LT used a technique called

"heuristic search," which means it made educated guesses about which logical steps might lead to the desired proof (Newell et al., 1959).

Achievements and Impact

The Logic Theorist's crowning achievement was proving 38 of the first 52 theorems from Whitehead and Russell's "Principia Mathematica." In fact, it even found a nicer, more elegant proof of Theorem 2.85 than the original, proving that machines not only equal but potentially surpassed human reasoning on specific domains (Simon & Newell, 1958).

The Logic Theorist was not the first AI program; it was a proof of concept that machines could solve intelligent reasoning. It opened, like Einstein's early papers on quantum theory, an entirely new field of possibilities. The results of its direct achievements reach beyond the specific achievements to the fundamental principles of the design of AI programs and problem solving methods.

ELIZA (1966): The Birth of Conversational AI

As Bohr's model revolutionised our understanding of atomic structure, ELIZA's revolutionised human-computer interaction by showing that machines could engage in what looks remarkably like human conversation. Created by Joseph Weizenbaum at MIT in 1966, ELIZA was not just a program; it was a watershed moment in computing history.

Development and Architecture

Joseph Weizenbaum created ELIZA at MIT, naming it after Eliza Doolittle from "Pygmalion." Think of ELIZA as a mirror that reflects your thoughts back to you - it did not understand conversations but rather used pattern matching to reformulate users' statements into questions (Weizenbaum, 1966).

Technical Implementation

ELIZA employed a technique called "pattern matching and substitution," similar to how a parrot might repeat what it hears but with slight modifications. For example:

- User: "I am feeling sad"

- ELIZA: "Why are you feeling sad?"

- User: "You don't understand me" Transform: [you -> I] [me -> you]

- ELIZA: "Why do you think I don't understand you?"

This simple yet effective approach created an illusion of understanding that was so convincing it led to what became known as the "ELIZA effect" - people's tendency to anthropomorphize computer behaviors (Shum et al., 2018).

Early Natural Language Processing

Early Natural Language Processing (NLP) in the 1960s was similar to attempts to understand the quantum nature of light: researchers discovered simple phenomena that were actually more complex than they appeared. This kind of period has set a basis for how machines would eventually process and understand how human language works.

Fundamental Approaches

Like the advanced foreign language of teaching to someone who has never spoken to another human being, early NLP researchers had to work out how to start from scratch. They had to break down language into its basic components: Chomsky (1965) used grammar rules (syntax), meaning (semantics), and (pragmatics) of context.

Chomsky's Revolution

In the late 1950s, Noam Chomsky brought the field of natural language processing in a direction it has not looked back from: by introducing transformational generative grammar. His work "Syntactic Structures" (Chomsky, 1957) challenged the prevailing behaviorist paradigm by proposing that language acquisition and processing involve innate mental structures rather than mere stimulus-response patterns.

On the basis of the idea that surface forms of sentences are generated out of deeper structural representations by a set of systematised transformations (Harris, 1968) the concept of transformational grammar proposed a formal description of language structure. This theory was a major force shaping early NLP systems as empirical models had tried to put these linguistic principles into computational models.

NLP system design benefited from the Chomsky (1965) distinction between competence and performance: that is, the difference between the abstract knowledge of language and the use of that language in its actual application. The parse algorithms he developed to show his emphasis on syntactic structures underpinning language understanding included devices to capture hierarchical linguistic relationships (Woods, 1970).

Chomskyan theories were, however, projected into NLP, but the practical implementation was challenging. Some researchers tried to approach a problem using alternative techniques (Schank & Abelson, 1977), since the complexity of transformational rules and the inability to handle the semantic interpretation made the traditional approach impracticable. However, Chomsky's work made the point of formal grammar for computational linguistics and has impacted subsequent work in parsing for grammars and grammars as formalisms (Kay, 1979).

There are contemporary NLP systems that attempt to process structured segments with structural hierarchy, and often use statistical or neural approaches, yet are still manifesting, however slightly, Chomsky's legacy through their focus on syntax and its patterns. Even now, his

theoretical framework continues to provide a haven for discussions pertained to artificial intelligence language representation and processing (Manning & Schütze, 1999).

Key Developments

1. Machine Translation: English – Russian translation system was demonstrated for the first time in the Georgetown – IBM experiment of 1954.
2. Syntactic Analysis: Development of various algorithms which parse a sentence so as to understand sentence structure.
3. Semantic Processing: Attempts to represent meaning in computer readable forms

Microworlds and Planning Systems

During the late 1960s and early 1970s, microworld phenomena represented a radical paradigm change within AI research. Microworlds were just like Rutherford's gold foil experiment that polished atomic investigation to its own controlled environment and so provided their controlled domains for studying the artificial intelligence problems.

Concept and Implementation

They were microworlds, scientific laboratories where researchers could run AI capabilities in controlled environments. SHRDLU (1970), run in a simple block world where it could figure out and carry out commands to move geometric shapes, was the most famous example (Winograd, 1972).

Planning Systems

A typical planning system such as the STRIPS (Stanford Research Institute Problem Solver) looked at problems much as a chess player thinks a few moves forward. They would:

1. Define the initial state
2. Specify the goal state
3. Generate a sequence of actions to reach the goal

Microworlds and planning systems represented a crucial phase in AI development, providing controlled environments for testing theories and developing algorithms. Like the early particle accelerators in physics, they allowed researchers to study complex phenomena in simplified settings, leading to fundamental insights that continue to influence modern AI systems.

Early Debates and Controversies

AI had its birth in the early 1950s and was primarily defined during its infancy by several debates that cast the framework for practise and thinking in the field. They help form research paradigms that define AI efforts for many successive decades as researchers scrambled to explain such phenomena.

The Machine Intelligence Debate

The first controversy stemmed from Turing's (1950) seminal paper which proposed the imitation game as a test of machine intelligence. This started a debate over what makes something intelligent, and at what point it becomes computational. On the one hand, Gödel and others like him were sceptical that human intelligence can be computed mechanically (Boolos, 1995); on the other, McCarthy and Minsky had first proposed the idea that machine intelligence is possible (McCarthy et al., 1955).

Heuristic vs. Algorithmic Approaches

There was a great debate between those favouring heuristic problem solving and those of formal algorithmic methods. Examples of heuristic search include Newell and Simon's contribution to the Logic Theorist (Newell et al., 1959), which showed that heuristic search had much power, and the claim that rigorous mathematical approaches were the only reliable course of conduct (Wang, 1960).

The Knowledge Representation Controversy

Some of the early AI researchers disagreed with how knowledge should be represented in machines. One was discussing Minsky's frames theory Minsky (1961), where structured representations were proposed, while others were calling for logical formalisms McCarthy (1963). These arguments provided the main driving force behind the evolution of initial manifestations of expert systems and problems solving applications.

Pattern Recognition vs. Reasoning

The battle between pattern recognition approaches and symbolic reasoning was initiated in the mid 1960's. Early neural network approach was Rosenblatt's perceptron (Rosenblatt, 1958) and formal logical reasoning (Nilsson, 1965) was emphasised by Nilsson. In a short time, Minsky and Papert (1969) later formulated the limitations of perceptrons, shifting focus initially from symbolic ones.

The Role of Language

Early AI research was marked by disagreements over what, if anything, the relationship between language and intelligence might be. However, Bar-Hillel's criticism (1960) of machine translation represented major problems in natural language processing. Others (such as Chomsky, 1965) stressed the need for syntactic structure.

Conclusion

At the dawn of this period, from the 1960s, artificial intelligence was in its pioneering age, with an almost boundless optimism about the potential of the technology and with foundational breakthroughs that shaped the field until now. Early systems like Logic Theorist and ELIZA may all seem very primitive compared to today's AI applications — from chess playing computers to modern chatbots — but they still laid the groundwork for modern AI.

The lessons we learned here were useful lessons about what was possible and what was not with the use of artificial intelligence. However, they showed that aspects of human intelligence could be achieved via sophisticated programming, but that true human like intelligence is an orders of magnitude more complex challenge than first hypothesised.

Boldly go where no human or AI has gone before!
Ferhat Sarikaya

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